

EXTENT OF IMPLEMENTATION OF BRIGADA ESKWELA: BASIS FOR A PROPOSED PLAN OF ACTION

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Abstract: This study aimed to find out the extent of implementation of Brigada Eskwela in GSC Elementary School for the Arts to be used as basis for a proposed plan of action. The study used the descriptive-survey method of research design. A survey questionnaire adapted by the researcher was used to gather the data needed. It was then validated by credible individuals and was administered to the respondents. Weighted arithmetic mean was the statistical tool utilized in order to treat the data. Based on the analysis of the gathered data, Brigada Eskwela in GSC Elementary School for the Arts was highly implemented in which the situation described was true most of the time. All the five areas under Brigada Eskwela which include Enrolment Preparation, School Leadership, Teacher, Learners, and Classroom Structuring/Physical Plant/Facilities were rated highly implemented by the respondents. The results of the study reveal that GSC Elementary School for the Arts still has to improve its practices and do more so that Brigada Eskwela will be very highly implemented.

Keywords: Prevalent conflict management style and the dominant school climate of public elementary school, Philippines.

1. INTRODUCTION

It is usually recognized that learning arises at birth and takes place in the home, school, and community. Compelling family commitment is from the principle that parents, teachers, and community members share accountability for the educational, physical, community, emotional, and behavioral development of youth. Family commitment nurtured through a careful process that embraced throughout the school. It authorizes adults to support student's progress, addresses any barriers to learning, and ensures career readiness.

Brigada Eskwela is a national program developed by the Department of Education as an activity in support of the opening of classes every June. The program pursues to inspire parents, teachers and other members of the local community to offer substantial and non-substantial resources and facilities in cleaning classrooms and school principles as well as doing negligible repairs on counters, barriers and other portion of the schoolroom to be responsible for an atmosphere beneficial to learning (Brigada Eskwela Manual for School Heads, p. 1).

The concept of Brigada Eskwela hinged from the Bayanihan spirit that is innate to Filipinos. Bayanihan involves the voluntary effort of members of the community to help co-members of that same community who are in need (Baluyot, 2013). Brigada Eskwela is not just limited to the very concept of Bayanihan where a transferring of one's nipa hut from one

place to another or reaping of one's rice field. This activity stresses the importance of creating a school facility and environment that was put together and conserved by the people, of the people, and for the people. Moreover, it enlarges the impression that appropriate care and maintenance of school facilities and properties are not the sole responsibility of the administrators and the personnel but also of the stakeholders – mainly the students and their parents (Sibayan, 2012).

Many studies have revealed that when parents and families are responding to their children school needs, their children do better. The local community members can act as role models and mentors and provide an additional layer of support and inspiration for students and teachers when they become involved in schools endeavors. There are some ways to create a family partnership with the school. Some focus in the school and others on parents as the most dynamic means in the conglomerate equation, but both methods target the same goal: programs that enlist all the members of a community in the learning of their children. (Epstein et al., 2009).

When people think of involvement in schools, they typically imagine a parent attending a PTA meeting or volunteering to help teachers in preparing classrooms for evaluation. Today, many teachers apprehend that this image is not perfect or fully wide-ranging of the parents of many of our children. Most parents work and are not at home during the day, and many do not have time to attend the school board or PTA meetings. Working parents, single, and married are frequently unable to join parent-teacher meetings during the school day and regularly discover it even more problematic to partake in homeroom meetings. Families with numerous children in different grade levels also find it tough to be involved in many separate meetings at unlike schools and even if their kids enrolled in the same institution. These are just some of the complications which hinder families to get involved in significant school activities like Brigada Eskwela.

With this biting reality, the researcher has long felt the need to undertake this study to find out the extent of implementation of Brigada Eskwela in GSC Elementary School for the Arts in order to come up with a plan of action which will strengthen the engagement of the people responsible for the total education of the Filipino children.

his study aimed to find out the extent of implementation of Brigada Eskwela and the plan of action to be proposed after the necessary data gathered.

Specifically, this study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the extent of implementation of Brigada Eskwela on:

1.1 Enrolment Preparation

1.2 School Leadership

1.3 Teacher

1.4 Learners

1.5 Classroom Structuring/Physical Plant/Facilities

2. What plan of action can be proposed based on the findings of the study?

This study based on the theory of Epstein wherein the parents, schools, and communities have related responsiveness and commitment to educating children (Epstein et al., 2009). Epstein's school-family-community partnership model stresses the roles of the school, the family, and the community in working collaboratively to guide the progress and education of children. She referred partnership ideal as an intersecting stimulus between the school, family, and social group in educating children with an effort of attaining academic achievement.

She further stresses that the overlapping spheres of influence demonstrate shared obligation of the school, family, and community for a child's triumph in school. The outside assembly of the overlapping domains of inspiration pattern distinguishes the child at the center within the family, school, and community as the focus (Figure 1). The number of competencies, ideas, practices, and other forces push the scopes together or pull the spheres apart resulting in the amount of commonality between the school, family, and community. Children interact with, stimulus, and influenced by their families, their schools and their communities.

The theory of overlapping spheres of influence proposes that instructors provide family-like schools, families create school-like homes, and community encourages school-like occasions and family-like services. Educators create family-like schools by identifying children as individuals and making them feel dear. Parents create school-like families by being aware of the importance of school and school-related activities while reassuring their child's educational realization. Communities provide school-like opportunities by underpinning and be acquainted with the efforts and success of students. Communities also provide family-like sceneries and happenings by inspiring and assisting the families.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study focused on determining the extent of implementation of Brigada Eskwela in GSC Elementary School for the Arts, Apopong, General Santos City. Furthermore, the survey method was used to gather the needed data and information. A survey questionnaire developed by the researcher administered to the teachers who were volunteers during the conduct of Brigada Eskwela. The respondents identified through complete enumeration.

The Significance of the Study

The study is of great help to the following sectors who have stakes and are involved and accountable for the sufficient conduct of the Brigada Eskwela program.

For the School Administrators, the findings of the study serve as their guide in improving and innovating their administrative functions most importantly their managerial skills and capabilities because they are the in-charge of the school in enhancing parents and community awareness of their perceived roles in education. Moreover, they will be able to find ways and means how to implement Brigada Eskwela so that it could be more beneficial to parents, teachers, and pupils.

For the teachers, who believe in the importance of home-school and community link programs, the result of this study can work for as the basis to find more ways and strategies to strengthen parents' involvement as well as the community in school-related activities.

For the parents, this study may lead them to a better understanding of their roles in the education of their children and further motivate them to fully understand the importance of home-school link programs because when children see their parents working together, it may increase their interests and enthusiasm to be in school. Thus, better performance in school and quality education achieved.

The pupils will likewise profit from the result of this study for they are the prime beneficiaries of it. They will know how significant is the participation of their parents for the success of Brigada Eskwela and will be able to encourage the latter to continue participating in the program in order to guarantee the children in an environment conducive to learning.

The outcome of this study is also beneficial to the community so it can contribute more to pupils, teachers, and families by offering services and integrating additional resources and programs to support learning and to improve the quality of education.

For the researchers, the study is of great help for those who want to venture in the same field of study for the satisfaction of their curiosity. It will purvey them some substantial accounts and relevant theories necessary for the accomplishment of their study.

For the Philippine Educational System specifically, the GSC Elementary School for the Arts, the importance of this study may be realized by key people in the educational setting. Results of the study will determine the areas of focus where the existing partnership between school, families, and community may further clearly emphasized and enhanced.

Definition of Terms

The following are some technical terms used by the researcher in the study. Thus, the researcher operationally defined them for of clarification.

The extent of Implementation refers to how well Brigada Eskwela has been implemented in GSC Elementary School for the Arts regarding its enrolment preparation, school leadership, teacher, learners, and physical plant and facilities.

Plan of Action is a sequence of steps taken or activities performed, for a program or strategy to succeed. This structured plan once carried out, will bring about changes and improvements in the conduct of Brigada Eskwela in GSC Elementary School for the Arts. The researcher will propose this plan based on the results of her study.

Brigada Eskwela refers to a program of the Department of Education which brings together the teachers, parents and community affiliates every third week of May to work together in fixing and getting ready public schools for school opening. During the several days of the event, volunteers take time out in doing petty maintenances, painting, and cleaning of school campuses (Brigada Eskwela Manual for School Heads, p. 2).

Volunteers are the school's partners in the conduct of Brigada Eskwela and may include teachers, parents, alumni associations, civic and social organizations, local government units, religious groups, business establishments, private individuals, skilled workers, and professional groups.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This following presents the views and literature on topics which are significantly related to the present study. Including other similar studies and researches are because of their bearing to the study and to provide sufficient background and information for this study.

Legal Bases of Brigada Eskwela

Brigada Eskwela, in reality, is a logical extension of the stated objectives of Republic Act 8525, also known as the Adopt-A-School Act of 1998. The law sponsored by Rep. Anne Marie Periquet at the House of Representatives. The late Sen. Marcelo Fernan wrote the Senate version. The law became very useful only in 2003 as part of the Oplan Balik Eskwela Program, when former Education Secretary Edilberto de Jesus effectively pushed for the declaration of essential implementing rules and regulations from the Bureau of Internal Revenue.

RA 8525 establishes the Adopt-A-School Program, "which allows private entities to support public schools, whether elementary, secondary, or tertiary... in, but not limited to, the following extents: staff and faculty improvement for training and further education; the building of amenities; upgrading of existing facilities, the endowment of books, periodicals and other instructional materials; and modernization of educational technologies."

As an incentive, RA 8525 provides that "prevailing laws to the contrary nevertheless, expenses acquired by the implementing entity for the "Adopt-A-School Program" shall allow an extra inference from the unrefined income equivalent to fifty percent (50 percent) of such expenditures."

This enticement is very important because the Internal Revenue Code already provides for a 100 percent tax deduction for expenses qualified to assistance earned by private entities to public schools, subject to certain conditions. RA 8525's additional 50 percent thus becomes a tasty piece of icing on the cake.

The volunteers do the operation clean-up drive on school surroundings, make the essential processes on classroom tables, and chairs and parents and private business offer the needed supplies and materials. This awe-inspiring involvement of private sectors and volunteers shows how populaces in the country pleasantly succeed the activity to achieve the common objective. It is a vital binder and devotion which helps progress the value of teaching and learning since classrooms will be enthusiastically accessible to accommodate the incoming school children. Parents, though it may be troublesome on their part, all the efforts are well rewarded for they will no longer disquiet about their children being bit by mosquitoes or getting sick because of the contaminated surroundings. Applying determination hand in hand, the Brigada Eskwela is the contemporary picture of the famous Bayanihan spirit where Filipinos value the significance of volunteerism in attaining the common end. It is a venue for societal and general public liberation by displaying unison and continuous social involvement (Capacio, 2013).

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Indeed, the Adopt-A-School Program (ASP) reports that “over the years, the Brigada Eskwela determination has progressed from a week-long cleaning-up and enhancement exercise to a jovial assembly of both internal and external stakeholders; teachers, students, parents, school officials, community members, local government officials, non-government organizations, church groups, and the private sector.”

In 2007 alone, Brigada Eskwela success a record high of 90% involvement among school societies, causing more than P2.5 billion worth of support in-kind and volunteer labor hours. It has confirmed to continue to achieve more mileage among communities, corporations, small-medium enterprises, government and non-government organizations and private individuals. Indeed, Brigada Eskwela is becoming DepEd’s ideal of sincere public and private partnership in action. As the Department activities to solve the many encounters facing Philippine education, Brigada Eskwela will serve as one of its combat zone ingenuities prompting every Filipino that we are all participants in education.

In some schools, fire and earthquake drills conducted. We laud all volunteers – individuals, civil society groups and NGOs who participated in this year’s Brigada Eskwela. The efforts, time and material contributions of these groups have momentarily contributed to its success. Their participation in the Brigada Eskwela ensured that our public schools –both elementary and secondary – are conducive for learning, safe and fully prepared for disasters for our pupils, students and teachers as well (Brigada Eskwela Manual for School Heads, p.4).

However, we noticed that some schools lacked the information drive in encouraging the participation of the community people and National Government Offices (NGOs). Letters of invitation were many late NGOs that are willing to participate in the Brigada Eskwela were not able to make it. Next time, we request that communities, in coordination with the village officials, should undertake a massive information campaign on Brigada Eskwela (Cortez, 2014).

Brigada Eskwela shall take part to the realization of the UNESCO- prescribed Education for All (EFA) aims that seek to intensify student contribution and lessen dropouts and to expand the quality of education in participating schools in order to upsurge student performance (DepEd Order 100, s.2009).

At the instant, Brigada Eskwela carries on to be the DepEd’s prominent summer activity that leaves stakeholders with a sense of completion and a nice, earnest feeling inside. However, Brigada Eskwela has so much more probable yet to be selected. The Adopt-A-School secretariat has taken an enormous step in the right course by writing up a “Brigada Eskwela Manual for School Heads.” This 18-page manuscript arranges for public school principals and school heads with a hands-on, step-by-step direction to getting the broadest community involvement for Brigada Eskwela.

As the Department actions to answer the many tasks facing Philippine education, Brigada Eskwela will serve as one of its forefront initiatives reminding every Filipino that we are all patrons in education.

Brigada Eskwela and Enrolment Preparation

“Education is indeed for all. Hence, it is just right to ask for everybody’s support to achieve the Education For All (EFA) target of the department. We believe that DepEd’s public-private partnership through the Adopt-A-School program will further benefit our 44,000 public schools and help the department deliver quality education services that our schoolchildren rightfully deserve,” said Education Secretary Armin Luistro as the Department of Education (DepEd) gears up for the strengthening of public-private partnerships (PPP) in education through the Adopt-A-School Program (ASP).

Luistro explained that “the very target of DepEd is to realize the intent and purpose of the UNESCO-prescribed EFA—especially the 6th and last goal, which is to “improve the quality of education.” It is for this intention that we endure calling on all education stakeholders, for us to realize the EFA goals by 2015.”

Home-school and community collaboration is the catchword of Brigada. Instead of waiting for the government to do repair and renovation, landscaping and beautification, parents and barangay officials congregate in schools for a few days to work hand in hand with school officials and teachers their output: Tidied up classrooms and sanitized surroundings, making the school environment conducive to teaching and learning (Doblon, 2011).

More significant than physical outputs, however, is the building up of a close interpersonal relationship between parents and school people. Such rapport is critical; without it, a handicapped school operation will happen. There are funds for building repair, it is true. These seldom trickle down to most schools especially those in rural areas. Always in a limited

amount, their release from year to year is never enough. School people are therefore forced to appeal to parents and local officials for help. Usually, support comes in the form of monetary contributions, but sometimes, as in the case of the Brigada, it also comes in the form of free personal services.

Usually, most parents in countryside areas are easy to mobilize for Brigada-like initiatives. Mostly farm workers are quick to respond to calls for volunteer work, especially if amenities like the provision of free meals. In the city, it is different. Perhaps because most parents are involved in their livelihood activities, recruiting them for school services is difficult. They do cooperate by way of chipping in a few pesos for contributions. Most school people are reluctant to pass the hat around for fear of complaints.

Macasinag (2012) stressed that Brigada Eskwela is more than just clean-up and repair or sprucing up of schools. It is also a forum for better education. Brigada Eskwela emphasizes the role of the community in improving public education and the voluntary participation of community stakeholders to give our public school students an environment that is more conducive for learning. The involvement of the community is a thrust of good and participative governance in this direction. This initiative is a manifestation of our empowerment as we move towards collectivity.

School Leadership

Leithwood (2015) defined school leadership as the method of soliciting and controlling the aptitudes and vitalities of teachers, pupils, and parents toward reaching common educational aims. Demands made on schools for advanced levels of pupil success and schools were likely to develop and transform. These expectations accompanied by calls for responsibility at the school level.

School leadership has very substantial effects on the worth of the school organization and pupil learning though there is one familiar case of a school productively turning around its pupil attainment path without the presence of talented leadership. One justification for this is that leadership catalyzes for unbridling the possible aptitudes that already is present in the organization. Those in governance roles have a remarkable obligation to “get it right (<http://illinoischoolleader.org/> retrieved February 20, 2015).

Strong Claims About Successful School Leadership

It is a summary of the fundamental findings of a review of literature carried out by the researchers as a point of departure for a large-scale empirical study organized from place to place what we denote to as ‘strong claims’ about effective school leadership. It includes: 1) School leadership is second only to classroom instruction as an encouragement on pupil learning, 2) Most effective leaders attract the same range of basic leadership culture, 3) The ways in which leaders bring into action these usual leadership norms display receptiveness to, rather than dictation by the contexts in which they work, 4) School leaders develop teaching and learning ultimately and most strongly through their guidance on staff motivation, guarantee and working circumstances, 5) School leadership, when broadly disseminated, has a better impact on schools and students, 6) Some configurations of spreading are more operational than others, and 7) A small handful of self-identities explains a high percentage of the deflection in leadership value (<http://dera.ioe.ac.uk/> retrieved February 20, 2015).

Teachers and Administrators Collaboration

Those in education know that universal change necessitates partnership, and when trying to device large-scale creativities like the Brigada Eskwela that require reconsidering specialized learning, set of courses and instructional materials, family commitment activities, valuation and other facets of the education scheme, cooperation is above all significant (Obrien, 2014).

Educators use the words "collaboration" and "partnership" moderately free, habitually giving little to no details on what explicitly good examples look alike. Obrien quoted a case study in 2011 that progressive, flexible relationships between teachers, their administrators, and unions, while cultivating public education found thirteen common subjects, including a) Emphasis on teacher quality containing proficient expansion, new systems of appraisal, peer-to-peer support, and mentoring programs, b) Focus on student performance with regions creating opportunities for teachers and administrators to come together and examine student presentation in order to categorize and concentrate on priority areas for development, c) Substantive problem-solving, innovation and willingness to experiment formulating recent ways to give attention to serious issues, with the partnership serving as a means for improvement (not as the end in itself), d) An organizational culture that

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Vol. 10, Issue 3, pp: (43-62), Month: May - June 2023, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

values and supports collaboration proven in part by leaders conversing on values of inclusion, engrossment and communication, as well as appreciation for teachers as professionals and for their coming together, and e) Collaborative structures at all levels in the district with an infrastructure that elevates and loosen up collaborative decision-making in schools through building-level leadership teams, school improvement committees, school advisory councils or other such bodies that meet on regularly and play a key role in site-based decision making (<http://www.edutopia.org/blog/when-teachers-and-administrators-collaborate-anne-obrien/> retrieved March 15, 2015).

The Role of School Administration in Parents' Participation

Administrator responsiveness appears to be the key to efficient parent participation in school's activities. Insider/outsider pressure reduced with an embracing school atmosphere: parent bulletin boards, easy access on computers, resource materials, an invitation to participate in scholastic activities. The administrator's part is to create a respectable climate and become more open to the public. Principals considered resilient role models for their staffs, and they must be conscious of the memoranda they send out.

Success needs support from all parties involved in the transformation process. Fullan (1991) (as cited by Vahedi, 2011) states that transformation in schools occurs when parents perform fundamental roles in the adjustment process. Using the term "decentralization" does not create change. It will only happen if parents signify their support in the decision-making. School staffs and parent communities must agree and dynamically participate in imperative for conversion to occur. Administrative and principals viewed as the key element in the realization or disappointment of school-based decision making and parent involvement. Principal support gives the idea to be indispensable in reaching suitable decisions for two reasons: response from school staffs is required, and the manner is reasonably dissimilar from the typical operating processes in traditional schools.

The administration must coordinate, manage, support, fund, and recognize parents' involvement in order for teachers to successfully involve the parents. Principals must reassure and simplify the building of reliance and related admiration between teachers and parents Butler (1992) (as cited by Vahedi, 2011).

Impact of Teachers' Preparedness to Student Learning

The significance of well-prepared teachers for student learning is incontestable. Prepared teachers are more intellectually able, rated as more effective by principals, supervisors, and colleagues, and enter and remain in teaching in greater numbers. In contrast, unprepared teachers have more classroom complications, rated less proficient by evaluators and associates, and retire at earlier points in their vocations. Whether equipped in old-fangled or alternative teacher education programs, well-prepared teachers are the foundation for ensuring that high-quality teachers are working in all classrooms (Cooper and Alvarado, 2015).

As cited earlier, the conditional determiner of whether a teacher is of "high quality" is student accomplishment. If the teacher is steadily fruitful in helping students to accomplish at or above predictable degrees of academic performance, then he or she can be well-thought-out effective and of high quality. Research shows that having an order of excellent teachers can help students dazed the shortfalls in their home environments (<http://www.unesco.org/> retrieved February 25, 2015).

School Plant and Facilities

Many schools are now compensating more consideration to their school plant. School plant which includes all edifying facilities has been steadily found to have a useful relationship with the quality of education. These educational amenities include the site, the buildings, physical equipment, leisure spaces and textbooks used for the reaching of educational purposes.

The school plant is the total of the building, paraphernalia, textbook including the surrounding where instruction and education take place. The school plant includes all permanent and semi-permanent structures in the school. (Peter, 2012).

Importance of School Plant and Classroom Structuring

Many researchers have shown the evident correlation between the school plant and curriculum, which in turn affects actual teaching and learning. The bearing of the physical milieu in which teaching-learning takes place is very significant. The motives for this are not implausible and include: 1) School plant helps improve students' performance in achievement tests,

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

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2) School plant improves attendance and reduces dropout rate, 3) School plant improves student's attitude to learning, 4) School plant increase teaches retention rate, and 5) It boosts teaching effectiveness (<https://namse.wordpress.com> retrieved February 15, 2015).

Odupurokan (2011) states that a well-planned school plant will mobilize projected outcomes of education, that will enable considerable social, political and economic liberation; efficacious teaching-learning and academic performance of learners. Consequently, it said that the school plant is an important feature of educational preparation because schools are well appropriate, buildings constructed, and equipment is provided.

Peter (2012) also stresses that the school plant is essential to achieving positive outcomes in the teaching-learning process. The school plant is the support and sustenance of all training and knowledge activities. The location, size, organization and other facets of the classroom, upkeep conveniences such as labs, toilets, and other equipment can either be friendly or disgusting to teachers and students alike. This simple fact has been noted to influence the acts of teaching and learning.

Improving Parent Involvement Levels

In their longitudinal work at the Center on School, Family and Community Partnerships at Johns Hopkins, Joyce Epstein, and her colleagues have moved the discussion of family-school relationships from one of involvement to one of partnership. Epstein (2001) (as cited by Soterno, 2009) explains that connection implies the expectation of the school for all parents to participate with the result that those who do take part are considered good parents and those who do not see as bad parents. "In partnership, educators, families and community members work together to share information, guide students, solve problems, and celebrate successes." Simon (2004) (as cited by Al-Taneiji, 2012) found that parents are more likely to be involved in their children's education if schools conduct activities/programs that encourage them to be involved.

Working With Families From Diverse Backgrounds

Functional school-family conglomerates to assist students from different populations. Educators are aware that families come in diverse configurations and have numerous viewpoints, prospects, and communication styles. Schools need to make education available to staff and families that encourage sympathetic and merriment of diverse family customs, beliefs, civilizations, etymological backgrounds, and socioeconomic statuses. When families and schools coach one another about their distinctive cultures, students see their worlds make even and working together in supporting their attainment (Lines, Miller, & Arthur-Stanley, 2010).

Partnering based on the statement that families, children, and mentors are doing the paramount they can. Hard works are made to comprehend others' conduct and purposes rather than judge them as right or wrong. Progressively, school-family partnerships seen as an indispensable constituent of efforts to address incongruences in educational outcomes. Schools enthusiastically work together with community resources (e.g., neighborhood associations, cultural leaders) in coordinating partnering efforts with families.

To successfully deal with the barriers preventing parental participation, schools need to provide openhearted weather where the school staff is deferential and approachable to parents. It is life-threatening that bureaucrats and teachers boost respectful two-way communication between the school and home. Bouie, an educational consultant, stated that the response is to stop considering parents like 'clients' and start treating them like 'partners' in facilitating children learn (Werry, 2009).

Promoting Family-School Partnerships

Koch (2014) stressed that families can spike partnerships with districts and schools by a) Gaining information about how school functions the learning and behavioral expectations of the students, and how they can support their students' learning, b) Sharing up-to-date contact information of a lead family member or guardian with the school office and teachers, especially a cell phone number and email address, c) Rendering voluntary service on a district/school/classroom committee or project, d) Attending in parent-teacher conferences or other school activities, e) Sharing with the district, school, and classroom family diversity strengths and needs at the beginning of every school year, and f) Communicating regularly with the district, school, and teachers to promote the total development of children and address any barriers to learning throughout the year.

In the efforts to enjoin schools with parents, educators can: a) include parents in classroom activities. Teachers can let families know how they can be helpful and can ask for their assistance with specific events. Parents can take part by preparing classroom materials, serving on committees, or sharing information about their careers or hobbies. The more involved parents are in what goes on in the classroom, the more likely they will comprehend the teacher's goals and practices, and b) communicate to parents at the beginning of the school year or semester about school policies and services. Inform them about classroom goals and give a few examples of what the children will be learning.

There are many reasons for developing the school, family, and community enterprises. They can increase school programs and school climate, offer family service and support, increase parent's assistance and leadership, join families with others in the school and the community, and help teachers with their work. However, the most important reason to generate such a partnership is to help all youngsters succeed in school and later in life. When parents, teachers, pupils, and others view one another as partners in education, a caring community forms round pupils and begins its work (Epstein, et al. 2009).

Community Involvement

Mendel (2005) (as cited by Midtimbang, 2012), the community is a central theme in the social studies curriculum during the early primary years. This theme builds on pupils' expanding knowledge of their communities by allowing them to explore their roles and the roles of others. Pupils' understanding of their communities is also a significant basis for learning about other communities-in other cultures, historical periods, and even in the animal kingdom.

He further added that school-family-community partnership is currently an innumerable issue for research in sociology, psychology, and education. Many researchers and academicians from many countries of the world have operated on it. Many researchers and theorists have considered the topic and support that accepting the connotations of school, family and community partnerships may open new educational outlooks, dimensions of trusting relationships, reinforce children's educational resources and sensitize about the usefulness of real cooperation.

According to Epstein and Sanders (2006) (as cited by Midtimbang, 2012), teachers and school leaders must be dynamic change mediators and team designers to guide their establishments in the preparation of future teachers who will conduct well-organized family and community involvement programs and practices. The school to be considered successful should become a change agent in the community. Schools make adoptions. They might conduct a few communications and collaborations with families and communities, keeping the three spheres of encouragement that unswervingly affect student learning and development relatively separate or they might conduct many high-quality collaborations and interactions planned to bring all three scopes of inspiration closer together. With recurrent interactions between schools, families, and communities, more pupils are more probable to receive mutual messages from various people about the reputation of the school, of working hard, of thinking imaginatively, of helping one another, and of remaining in school.

With several studies and work in over 100 journals, Epstein emphasizes on school, family, and community enterprise programs that will increase policy and practice to intensify student theoretical triumph and student realization. Epstein has recognized six major types of parental involvement: parenting, communicating, volunteering, learning at home, decision making, and collaborating with the community (Epstein et al., 2009).

In order to stimulate partnerships with the community, teachers can a) Welcome valid and dependable Learning Supports recognized by the school leadership into their classroom including but not restricted to programs/strategies, co-teaching and conference, b) Associate with local businesses when suitable to arrange for opportunities for work-related capability such as internships, computer-generated job interviews, or long-term occupation, c) Provide a classroom-based coordination to community partners to warrant that they have the essential information to complete work agreed upon, and d) Communicate on a regular basis with community partners to make sure continued progress headed for goals (Koch, 2014).

The Concept of Home-School and Community Partnership

Parental involvement and home-school and community trusts have been explored and addressed at the national, state, and local levels. In the face of the research of this topic, there is still apprehension regarding parental participation and what constitutes real parental engrossment in the education of students. Educators, parents, and public members may have different ideas regarding operative involvement rehearses and the ways each can contribute to educational development. Demarcations of parental involvement have been determined by schools, with slight or no input from parents or members

of the community. These school-centered definitions found in both research and practice and many agree that they do not completely express the variety of parental involvement practices Jordan, Orozco, & Averett, (2002) (as cited by Mendoza, 2013).

The school is responsible for keeping parents informed about it, how it functions, school-related events and the ways parents can participate. When schools create a constructive climate by reaching out to families and providing structures for them, parents and families feel that they are welcome.

Hanley-Maxwell et al. (2010), identified a basis for the Five Principles on Family-School collaboration. The first one is that families are constant in children's lives must be equal partners in all decisions affecting the child's educational program. Next, family involvement includes a wide range of family structures. Third, diversity and individual differences among people are to be valued and respected. The fourth one is that all families have strengths and coping skills identified and enhanced and lastly, families are sources of wisdom and knowledge about children.

According to Jenny (1997) (as cited by Soterno, 2009) schools work best when they work in partnership with parents and with the community. Parents who informed on school activities will be more willing to support the role of education and activities of their local school.

Actively involving parents in their child's learning at school and or home will show the school as well as the kids, that parents value education. It does not just affect their child's learning but also helps their child develop self-esteem, social skills, decent behavior, and healthy ways to enjoy their free time.

Researchers have confirmation for the constructive effects of parent's taking part on children, families, and school when schools and parents unceasingly support and boost the children's learning and development. According to Henderson and Berla (1994) (as cited by Olsen, 2010), "the most accurate analyst of a student's achievement in school is not earnings or social standing, but the degree to which that student's family can: a) bring into existence a home setting that heartens learning, b) express high perspectives for their children's success and future vocation, and c) get involved in their children's education at school and in the community.

Home-School-Community Partnerships

It is widely recognized that learning begins at birth and takes place in the home, school, and community. Eloquent family commitment based on the evidence that parents, educators, and community members share obligation for the academic, physical, social, emotional, and behavioral progress of youth. Family engagement nurtured through a thoughtful process that is restrained throughout the school. It authorizes adults to support student growth, addresses any obstacles to learning, and guarantees college and career inclination. Notably, effective family commitment systems, policies, and practices are mindful of different school-communities that are rich in language, culture, and school experiences. They are receptive to student and family needs (Koch, 2014).

He added that assimilating family engagement determination with learning and healthy growth is imperative to reaching positive student results. Manifold opportunities exist for districts and schools to partner with families which contain but are not limited to: a) promoting academic, physical, social, emotional, behavioral development and a conducive school climate, b) engaging and re-engaging learners, and c) addressing hurdles to learning.

Family engagement efforts should be united and reinforced across all areas of the school including complete planning, prospectus, lessons, valuation, leadership, environments for learning, and professional improvement.

Moreover, he also stressed that family commitment also occurs at home and in the community. Families assist learning and sound development in diverse ways, including but not limited to: a) showing they value education and healthy development, b) monitoring/assisting with homework completion, c) divulging their children to a assortment of learning opportunities (e.g., educational camps, public libraries, and museums), d) providing nurturing relationships, e) establishing routines, and f) maintaining expectations.

Family and Community Connections

Conventionally, parents were left to discover if they wanted to be aware of the schools and their children's education -- and then figure out ways to become involved. The weight of engagement was placed directly on the shoulders of parents and

family members. A comparatively new and influential idea is that schools must take on this accountability. Schools are now becoming functionally involved in manipulating strategies to involve the community and families in the education of their children (http://www.thirteen.org/edonline/concept2class/familycommunity/index_sub3.html retrieved January 22, 2015).

Educators have usually directed parents -- particularly mothers -- as the topmost active support for students in school. Latest research done by the Harvard Family Research Project has found that members of the extended family, including siblings, often work with school children. Merely pointing parents does not sufficiently apprehend what is happening in many families. There are many occurrences where grandparents are in charge of nurturing a child and have the time to attend parent-teacher meetings.

The role of parent volunteers has also seen an extension. It has moved from highlighting on classroom assistant and helpers to include families taking part in fundraising, working as school promoters, and acting as negotiators of educational transformation.

Schools are also now introducing their doors for more community resources to assist students and families. The presence of "full-service schools" or "school-linked services" shows that schools are giving attention not only to the speculative needs of students but their whole development. These full-service schools offer a far-reaching variety of health, counseling, social services, and after-school programs that deepen student learning and growth. They also sustain family immersion through parenting assemblies, adult education, and training for management positions in school groups.

Also, some schools are undertaking makeover through community-initiated activities. These communities are taking responsibility to use evidence about schools to offer renewed viewpoints on school upgrading. They are conveying with schools on new results to frequent problems. Schools are launch to change in ways that carry more voices to the decision-making table.

Benefits of Family and Community Connections

There are plentiful welfares from well-implemented school and community partnership programs. They include augmented student attendance, higher realization and report-card grades, a sense of better security, fewer social problems, and an upturn in positive approaches about school and schoolwork (http://www.thirteen.org/edonline/concept2class/familycommunity/index_sub4.html retrieved January 22, 2015).

Research finds that involvement of parents tends to weaken as students get older unless school programs are put in place to inspire it. Well-to-do communities tend to have better influences on schools. Shoddier communities need to establish programs that reach out to parents to intensify involvement. Poor communities tend to have more undesirable insights about parent involvement; this mostly happens because, without a scheduled program, interactions tend to befall when students have complications or in trouble.

The readings also find that utmost families are anxious with their children's education and want to help them do well in school. Just about all teachers and superintendents express concern in augmented parental and community involvement. Despite their mutual interest in helping children get to the top, however, teachers and parents may not interconnect with each other, in part because of previous qualms and frustrations experienced by both sides. Blameless family-and-school partnership programs work to overcome these trials so that all parents can be involved in their children's education across the grades in positive ways. Planned partnership programs are needed to ensure the same participation by school, family, and community -- rich or poor.

Benefits for the Children

Parent involvement has several advantages for school children. These include the facts that children tend to achieve more, regardless of ethnic or racial background, socioeconomic status, or parents' education level. They generally achieve better grades, test scores, and attendance, consistently complete their homework, have healthier self-esteem, more self-disciplined, and demonstrate higher ambitions and enthusiasm toward school, and enrich behavior in school and less suspension for penalizing reasons. Fewer children are placed in exceptional education and educative classes. Children from unlike racial upbringings tend to do better when parents and professionals work together to connect the gap between the beliefs at home

and in school. Usually, junior high and high school students whose parents continue to get involved make better shifts and are less likely to give up school.

Benefits for the Parents

Being involved in school also benefits the parents themselves. Parents escalate their communication and conversation with their children and are more approachable and thoughtful to their children's social, emotional, and academic, developmental needs. They become more confident in their parenting and decision-making skills, increase knowledge on child development, there is more use of friendliness and confident support and less castigation on their children, and have a better grasp of the school core curriculum and teacher's job. When parents are conscious of what their children are learning, they are more expected to help when they are invited by teachers to turn into more involved in their children's learning activities at home. Parents' observations of the school are better-quality, and there are resilient ties and obligation to the school. They are more cognizant of and become more active regarding, policies that have an emotional impact their children's education when parents members of the decision-making team.

Benefits for the Educators

When schools have a high proportion of involved parents in and out of schools, teachers and principals are more likely to experience higher morale. Teachers and principals often receive countless respect for their profession from the parents. Unfailing parent involvement leads to enhanced communication and relations between parents, teachers, and administrators. Teachers and principals obtain an improved understanding of families' cultures and diversity, and they form deeper respect for parents' capabilities in time. Principals and teachers report an increase in job gratification.

Benefits for the School

Schools that dynamically involve parents and the community has deliberately established better reputations in the community and in return they experience better community support. School platforms that reassure and involve parents usually do healthier and have sophisticated quality programs that parents are not involved.

According to Lass (2011) (as cited by Mendoza, 2013) outside the home, parents can function as promoters for the school. They can undertake to help out with school actions or work in the classroom, or they can take an energetic role in the domination and decision-making essential for planning, developing and providing an education for the community's children.

Luster (2010) (as cited by Mendoza, 2013) added that after many years of intense effort to increase parent's involvement in schools, the results are beginning to appear in the educational research. The news is good for schools where parent's participation is high, and the welfare for children is promising. When schools involve parents, children have advanced ratings and consistent test scores, improved manners at home and school, and better social skills and adaptation to school.

Plunkett (2011) said that some programs intend to touch parents who do not usually partake in their children's education. Such programs provide supple planning for school events and parent-teacher consultations, inform parents about what their children are learning, and help parents form a sympathetic environment for children learning at home.

He further stressed that some parents who are uninvolved in school may not understand the importance of parent's envelopment or may think they do not have the skills to be competent to help. Even parents who are self-assured and eager to help may vacillate to become involved for the fear of surpassing their confines. Raising the spirit of parents' involvement is one great responsibility of teachers and school administrators.

The recommendations offered in this publication can help teachers involve parents who might not otherwise be involved. Whereas it is likely for an educator to implement such a parent involvement program alone, it is much easier if the school as a whole is devoted to the program. Organizational staff can disburden the implementation of a comprehensive parent involvement program and can offer help and support to teachers according to Melanson (2009).

Jackson (2011) said that schools recognize that the first and most significant influence on a child's learning and that unrelenting participation in their education is essential if they are to complete the best learning outcomes. It is well-known that students with attentive and involved parents do better at school. While one may be involved in a child's learning at

home, he/she can contribute by participating in the school council, joining the parent club, or getting involved in less formal school activities.

The study conducted by Smith (2010) (as cited by Mendoza, 2013) aimed to distinguish the strong point and deficient qualities of the current practices of parental involvement in school as judged by the parents, teachers, and administrators, find out the distinctiveness of parents towards parental participation in the education of the pupils, become sensitive of the common obstructions to parental involvement in school and plan a program that will further heighten the engrossment of the parents in school.

When parents are the concern in their children's education, both children and parents are expected to help. Scholars report that parent's participation in their children's schooling frequently enhances children's self-esteem, improves children's academic achievement, improves parent-child relationships, and helps parents develop positive attitudes towards school and a better understanding of the schooling process (<http://www.ericdigests.org> retrieved October 12, 2014).

Despite these compensations, it is not always easy for parents to find a time and drive to become involved or match up with schedules for school happenings. For some parents, a visit to the school is considered as a rough experience, perhaps a relic from their school days. Others may have their hands occupied with their jobs and other children. The cost and availability of babysitters are other factors. Recently, teachers and other school staff have made distinctive determinations to increase communication with parents and boost involvement in children's learning proficiencies (Jabar, M. 2010).

The good school-community relationship offers valuable means of gaining public understanding and support of the school's educational program. The school principal's consciousness of the community activities encourages the exercise of leadership on the part of the teacher-members and the people without relinquishing total responsibilities for the operation of the school (Midtimbang, 2012).

SYNTHESIS

Educating the youth is such a critical job. The community, the parents especially, are duty bound to join hands with school people. It is not only for sprucing up the school environment that parents and teachers should come together. It is also for the more important job of collaborating to give their children the best that education can offer – intellectual sharpening and character building. Teachers have been professionally honed to accomplish these objectives, but without the active support of parents and the community, their efforts will have only limited impacts. Specifically, such backing up may be in the form of encouragement to their children to study their lessons or in the form of provisions for learning materials and to participate in valuable school activities.

The meaningful involvement of parents and community in children's training can cultivate the educational progression. Parents can contribute discernments and familiarity that supplement the specialized skills of schools' staffs in ways that reinforce academic and social programs. However, for parent's involvement ingenuities to be fruitful, they should be part of a contextually focused school development practice intended to generate constructive relationships that support children's overall development. Parents and community involvement programs instituted in the customary organization and unbending school environments are less likely to produce positive results than those that are part of a more cooperative organizational structure. In our work, we include parents and community at all levels of school life through general support of schools' educational programs, active participation in daily activities, school planning, and management. They work composed with schools' staffs to form academic and social goals and to develop and implement extensive school plans.

Surely, Brigada Eskwela has been organized and implemented for advancing professional, administrative, and leadership expertise of administrators and teachers of public schools where both are given the chance and the break to agree and converse with people in various walks of life – properly educated or otherwise. Second, it has also helped toughen the relationship of the school to the community where it is located. It is a Department of Education sanctioned activity which encourages the collaboration of stakeholders in bringing the spirit of volunteerism. The program embraced by different organizations supported by the active participation of the parents. For these educational outcomes, the Brigada Eskwela deserves support from all sectors of society.

3. MATERIAL AND METHODS

This study utilized the descriptive survey method of research. It was availed for this study because the goal of the researcher is to determine the extent of implementation of Brigada Eskwela in GSC Elementary School for the Arts. As supported by Fraenkel and Wallen (2009), this kind of design is employed to describe what people think, do, or believe.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in GSC Elementary School for the Arts situated at Purok 7 New Society, Barangay Apopong, General Santos City. The school is a public institution under the Department of Education. It has a population of 2, 107 pupils from kindergarten to grade six with 26 teachers and one principal under one district supervisor for the school year 2014 – 2015. Most of the residents are handful businessmen, some are tricycle drivers, and some are professionals. Almost all members of the teaching staff of the school are residents of the barangay. It is a notable school in the Division of General Santos City because of its Enhanced Arts Program. It created intended for the poor yet gifted children who inclined in music and arts and whose parents cannot manage to pay for sending them to schools offering such a unique program.

The respondents of the study were the teachers of GSC Elementary School for the Arts who participated in the conduct of Brigada Eskwela. The complete enumeration used in order to obtain the total number of respondents.

To answer the problems raised, the researcher used one (1) set of the instrument to obtain the needed data. The tool contains questions regarding the implementation of Brigada Eskwela. It serves as an indispensable tool in verifying each claim and providing reliability of the data at hand. It gives pertinent information for the completion of the study.

Survey Questionnaire – this is the primordial instrument used in this study. It was designed and framed for determining the extent of implementation of Brigada Eskwela and was primarily used to secure valid accounts for the subproblems presented.

The questionnaire in determining the extent of implementation of Brigada Eskwela reworked from the Department of Education Enclosure 4 to Regional Memorandum No. 105 s. 2014: Brigada Eskwela On-Site Monitoring & Evaluation Tool and from the Department of Education Region XII Form A.1: Classroom Structuring Form, modified by the researcher in consultation with her adviser and was validated by five competent and highly credible people for possible enrichments and revisions. It was validated using the following sets of criteria: clarity of directions and terms, presentation/organization of the items, suitability, and adequateness of the items per category and purpose to ensure the credibility and veracity of the questionnaire at hand.

In identifying the extent of implementation of Brigada Eskwela, a five-point Likert scale survey questionnaire was used as basis for scoring. After getting the mean scores in every indicator: Enrolment Preparation, School Leadership, Teacher, Learners, and Classroom Structuring/Physical Plant/Facilities, all grand means were then added up and divided into 5. Consequently, a distinct interpretation of the results was determined based from the given arbitrary mean range.

Interpretation of the Weighted Mean Results

Weight	Arbitrary Mean Range	Interpretation
5	4.21-5.00	Very Highly Implemented
4	3.41-4.20	Highly Implemented
3	2.61-3.40	Moderately Implemented
2	1.81-2.60	Less Implemented
1	1.00-1.80	Not Implemented

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Extent of Implementation of Brigada Eskwela on Enrolment Preparation

Enrolment Preparation is generally highly implemented with a mean score of 3.39. The data under this area show that the mean ranges from 3.30 to 4.04. Seven (7) out of nine (9) indicators rated highly implemented; make volunteers aware of the importance of participating in Brigada Eskwela through public advertisements or media and education caravan (3.48), network with stakeholders and community for possible assistance (3.44), encourage families and communities to be

involved in a variety of ways (3.52), manage to have a kick-off ceremony to formally start the implementation of the program (4.04), conduct orientation to provide information to volunteers as part of the implementation (3.44), observe strict adherence to NO COLLECTION POLICY (3.41), and conduct enrolment in school, purok, barangay (3.48).

Also, a couple of items were found moderately implemented; observe the conduct of family mapping by purok or barangay (3.37) and solicit old bags, uniforms, shoes and other materials from more affluent families and share to less privileged pupils (3.30).

Based on the results, items which were rated highly implemented indicate that the situations are accurate most of the time. The respondents were able to participate very well in the above-mentioned indicators. Furthermore, items rated as moderately implemented show that the situations are real at average times. It implies that some of the respondents are not able to neither observe nor encounter teachers who conducted the family mapping. The respondents are not informed very well about the solicitation of school materials to share with the less fortunate children. Hence, these two indicators got the lowest mean scores under enrolment preparation.

The results conform to what Doblón (2011) had stated that home-school and community collaboration are the catchwords of Brigada Eskwela. Instead of waiting for the government to do repair and renovation, landscape and beautification, parents and barangay officials congregate in schools for a few days to work hand in hand with school officials and teachers their output: Tidied up classrooms and sanitized surroundings, preparing the school environment and making it conducive to teaching and learning.

The Extent of Implementation of Brigada Eskwela on School Leadership

School Leadership got a weighted mean result of 3.49 which indicate a high implementation at GSC Elementary School for the Arts. Based on the results, it could be gleaned that the respondents rated highly implemented the five (5) essential items; 1) involve parents/guardians in revising/updating school plans (3.89), 2) provide a school resource directory for parents/guardians and pupils with information on school services and programs (3.56), 3) observe collaboration among the administrator, teachers, stakeholders, and to all those who are part of the program's implementation (3.48), 4) recognize volunteers for their time and effort (3.63), and prepare Brigada Eskwela reports for submission (3.78).

However, moderately implemented as evaluated by the respondents were found in the following indicators: 1) provide training or assistance to all of those who want to know more about Brigada Eskwela, not just to the few who can attend meetings at school (3.26), 2) establish clear two-way channels for communications from home to school and from school to home (3.26), 3) document the actual implementation of the program from the first day up to the last (3.26), and 4) create a flexible volunteering and school event schedules, enabling parents who work to participate (3.26).

The results indicate that GSC Elementary School for the Arts' leadership is effective most of the time. The school was able to encourage the involvement of parents/guardians in school activities, inform them about the school's services and programs, and recognize them for their help and support. However, some of the situations under school leadership observed at average times. It means that even if the school is already gaining support from parents/guardians and stakeholders, it still has to do more in establishing communications between home and school and create a flexible schedule in order for all parents/guardians to participate in all the school's endeavors.

It supports the idea of Butler (1992) (as cited by Vahedi, 2011), that the administration must coordinate, manage, support, fund, and recognize parent's involvement in order for schools to successfully generate support from parents. Principals must inspire and ease the building of trust and common respect between teachers and parents.

Also, teachers and school leaders must be dynamic change mediators and team builders to guide their associations in the preparation of future educators that will conduct operational family and community involvement programs and practices. The school to be considered successful should become a change agent in the community and GSC Elementary School for the Arts is closed to achieving success if it will continue to improve its practices and engage family and community in all its endeavors Epstein and Sanders (2006) (as cited by Midtimbang, 2012).

The Extent of Implementation of Brigada Eskwela on Teacher

Data shows that this area was rated highly implemented by the respondents with a grand mean of 3.41. Three (3) items were rated highly implemented which include structuring classrooms based on Form A.1 Classroom Structuring Monitoring Form (3.44), observing the preparation of lesson plans, curriculum guides, class records, school registers, and class

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 10, Issue 3, pp: (43-62), Month: May - June 2023, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

programs (3.59), and working with enthusiasm and dynamism at all times (3.59). With these results, it could glean that teachers of GSC Elementary School for the Arts devote their time, money, and strength to prepare their classrooms as well as the needed materials for a smooth transition of classes throughout the school year.

Moreover, two (2) items were rated moderately implemented. These are the provision of relevant, durable, usable and well-presented instructional support materials for teachers and pupils (3.30) and awareness of the policies imposed by the Department of Education (3.15). Though the teachers provided instructional support materials for themselves and the pupils, some of them only created short-lived or temporary devices. More so, some teachers have observed that other co-workers do not religiously follow the policies imposed by the department which include the wearing of a prescribed uniform, attendance, punctuality, updating and submitting of records and forms on or before the deadline given.

The results imply that teacher's preparedness, awareness of central policies, and diligence in preparing instructional devices, lesson plans, and school forms matter for them to provide quality instruction to their clientele. The status of well-prepared teachers for student learning is incontestable. Better organized teachers who are more academically able are rated as more effective by principals, supervisors, and colleagues, and remain in teaching in greater number. In contrast, less well-prepared teachers have more classroom problems, evaluated less proficient by evaluators and colleagues, and leave at much-advanced rates at earlier points in their professions. Whether arranged in traditional or alternative teacher education programs, well-prepared teachers are the foundation for ensuring that high-quality teachers are working in all classrooms (<http://www.unesco.org/> retrieved February 25, 2015).

The Extent of Implementation of Brigada Eskwela on Learners

From the data presented, it shows that the area which got a weighted mean result of 3.69 was rated highly implemented by the respondents. The mean scores obtained ranges from 3.26 to 4.19. The following relevant items rated highly implemented by the respondents; monitor the present enrolment rate (4.15), check pupils' actual attendance (3.44), monitor the number of pupils in each class (3.48), inform pupils of their progress through the distribution of Form 138 every grading period (4.19), update learners about the latest policies (3.59), and provide guidance and counseling to pupils who need it (3.70). These indicators were observed most of the times by the respondents since these are few of their responsibilities as classroom teachers.

The results anchored to what Jackson (2011) had said that recognizing schools as the first and most significant influence on child's learning and that sustained participation in their education is imperative if they are to complete the best potential learning outcomes.

On the other hand, only one item has a rating of moderately implemented. It is the conduct of home visitation to potential dropouts and pupils with behavioral problems (3.26). It means that teachers should strengthen their guidance services and conduct home visitation to those pupils who are problematic in school. It is one way to associate the gap between school and home for students, families, and teachers. An increasing amount of inquiry points to the importance of parents assisting their children's learning in the home. A home visit is one way to excavate the trust between teacher and parent and proliferate the students' chances for success (Kilgore, 2014).

Furthermore, Simon (2004) (as cited by Al-Taneiji, 2012) found that parents are more likely to be involved in their children's education if schools conduct activities/programs that encourage them to be involved. Home visitation creates a partnership among educators and family members so they can work together to share information, guide students, solve problems, and celebrate successes.

The Extent of Implementation of Brigada Eskwela on Classroom Structuring/Physical Plant/Facilities

Data revealed that this area obtained a grand mean of 3.44 which indicates that it was rated highly implemented by the respondents. The mean scores range from 3.11 to 4.48.

One of the indicators was rated very highly implemented; display framed portrait of the current Philippine President, framed motto and relevant pictures, framed copy of the National Anthem and Pledge of Allegiance to the Philippine flag (4.48). This indicator was observed at all times and was accomplished by all classroom teachers in GSC Elementary School for the Arts. Furthermore, most of the gauges were rated highly implemented. Precisely, these include; post notice at the entry of each classrooms showing the grade and section occupying the room and the name of the class adviser (3.63), display

mounted copy of the class program on the door at adult eye level (3.59), set up reading, health and guidance corners in each classroom (3.89), observe functional water facilities with jug, glasses, basin, soap dish and towel in every teaching space (3.70), display classroom-based data of the Basic Education Information System with the presence of 8 modules which have updated, complete and systematically organized data (3.67), observe enhancement of the physical plant/facilities like classrooms, seats, water and sanitation, school ground, school's ID and name, etc. (3.74) and post the Department of Education's unified vision and mission (3.74). The mean scores only reflect that GSC Elementary School for the Arts has implemented the above mention indicators most of the time for it got very satisfactory ratings from the respondents. Lastly, only two (2) of the pointers under this area were rated moderately implemented; install chalkboard at an elevation which is in accord with the maximum comfortable reach of the children, properly framed, accurately lined and with curtains and chalk ledge (3.11) and post signage "This School is a Zone of Peace" at the entrance of the school (3.19). These situations were observed by the respondents at average times knowing the fact that some of the chalkboards are not standard in height and do not have ledges. Moreover, though the signage "This School is a Zone of Peace" is posted, it is only seen during the first semester of the school year posted until the end of the year.

The results support Odupurokan (2011) study that a well-planned school plant will mobilize anticipated results of education that will assist virtuous social, political and economic liberation; actual lessons and education and educational enactment of students. Therefore, it said that the school plant is an indispensable feature of educational preparation because schools are well-suited, buildings effectively built and equipment sufficiently provided much teaching and learning may not occur.

Peter (2012) further added that school plant is essential to achieving positive outcomes in the teaching-learning process. The school plant is the support and sustenance of all teaching and learning undertakings. The location, size, organization and other features of the classroom, support services such as labs, toilets, and other tools can either be openhearted or revolting to teachers and students alike. This modest fact has been renowned to genuinely encourage the actions of teaching and learning.

The Extent of Implementation of Brigada Eskwela on Enrolment Preparation, School Leadership, Teacher, Learners, and Classroom Structuring/Physical Plant/Facilities.

The data show that the mean ranges from 3.39 to 3.69 an indication that the respondents rated highly implemented in all the indicators which include; Enrolment Preparation (3.39), School Leadership (3.49), Teacher (3.41), Learners (3.69), and Classroom Structuring/Physical Plant/Facilities (3.44).

Generally, Brigada Eskwela in GSC Elementary School for the Arts was highly implemented in which the situation described was practiced most of the time as indicated by its grand mean which is equal to 3.48. However, the results show that even if Brigada Eskwela was already highly implemented, all areas still have to be improved to be fully implemented and be practiced at all times.

From the results, among the five areas evaluated to determine the extent of Brigada Eskwela's implementation, enrolment preparation got the lowest mean of 3.39. It implies that the school and its working committees should think of various ways in order to improve in this area. GSC Elementary School for the Arts can continue its best practices, treat its lapses, and network with potential stakeholders for enrolment preparation to upgrade its level of implementation.

According to Jenny (1997) (as cited by Soterno, 2009) schools work best when they work in partnership with parents and with the community. Parents informed on school activities will be more willing to support the role of education and activities of their local school.

Moreover, as stated by Epstein and Sanders (2006) (as cited by Midtimbang, (2012), teachers and school leaders must be dynamic change representatives and team builders to facilitate their institutions in the preparation of forthcoming educators who will conduct real family and community involvement programs and practices. The school to be considered successful should become a change agent in the community. Schools make adoptions. They possibly will conduct only limited communications and collaborations with families and communities, keeping the three scopes of stimulus that directly affect student learning and improvement relatively separate, or they might conduct many excellent communications and connections planned to bring all three domains of encouragement closer together. With recurrent interactions between schools, families, and communities, more pupils are possible to receive collective messages from various people about the prominence of school, of working hard, of thinking imaginatively, of assisting one another, and of continuing in school.

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 10, Issue 3, pp: (43-62), Month: May - June 2023, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

Therefore, GSC Elementary School for the Arts should continue its best practices, interact and communicate with all the people involved in children's education, and sustain the operational conduct of Brigada Eskwela for it to be very highly implemented throughout the year.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following are recommended.

The Department of Education should maximize Brigada Eskwela's potential as a venue for community involvement in education. Brigada Eskwela should be done the whole year, must not be limited to school maintenance, and should address pupil's participation and performance. The school's division offices should ensure a synchronized schedule of activities and strictly monitor the conduct of each doings in line with Brigada Eskwela. They should serve as catalysts for achieving higher outcomes they want for their schools. Schools should expedite necessary procedures to build up promotion campaign in all levels from schools, schools division, and regional offices to produce possible support from stakeholders and strengthen partnership and involvement of various stakeholders to gain more support of interest.

The school principal shall take the lead in designing the activities for Brigada Eskwela to promote harmless school environment and to ensure the participation of teachers, parents, community members, local authorities and other concerned stakeholders. As the school administrator, he/she must think of that school upgrading does not end on the final day of the Brigada Eskwela week. It is a continuous activity to guarantee the school children of an environment favorable to learning. As a means of satisfying the Brigada Eskwela efforts, the principal should communicate with and appoint all teachers, pupils, and parents to satisfy their conforming roles and do their share principally those that were donated by associates and helpers during Brigada Eskwela.

There should be a proper organization of Brigada Eskwela steering and working committees so they can perform their functions religiously to obtain outstanding results from the pre-implementation, implementation, up to the post-implementation stage. Moreover, committees should be able to promote public awareness and encourage involvement, generate resources, materials and labor, direct and monitor the conduct of activities, provide administrative support and manage Brigada Eskwela funds, and lastly, to document and prepare required reports for submission.

An action plan must be proposed, adopted, and implemented to provide informed recommendations as well as to continue and to improve the conduct of Brigada Eskwela from planning to mobilizing volunteers, resources, and goodwill to fully implement the various stages of the program.

6. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were drawn:

Generally, the extent of implementation of Brigada Eskwela in GSC Elementary School for the Arts was highly implemented in which the situation described was practiced most of the time as indicated by its grand mean. Enrolment preparation, school leadership, teacher, learners, and classroom structuring/physical plant/facilities were all highly implemented.

There is still a room for improvement for the GSC Elementary School for the Arts to implement Brigada Eskwela practices at all times throughout the whole duration of the program.

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International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

 Vol. 10, Issue 3, pp: (43-62), Month: May - June 2023, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

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REFERENCES

- [1] Al-Taneiji, S. (2012). The Role of Leadership in Engaging Parents in United Arab Emirate School. *International Education Studies*; Vol. 6, No. 1, p. 154
- [2] Baluyot, R. (2013). Brigada Eskwela. Retrieved October 21, 2014, from <http://udyong.net/teachers-corner/662-brigada-eskwela>.
- [3] Brown, P. (n.d.) Eric Digest. Involving Parents in the Education of Their Children. Retrieved March 15, 2015 from <http://www.ericdigests.org/pre-9212/parents.htm>
- [4] Capacio, A. (2013). Brigada Eskwela: Awakening People Empowerment. Retrieved October 20, 2014, from <http://www.depedmalaybalay.net/info/brigada-eskwela-awakening-people-empowerment.html>.
- [5] Cooper, J. & Alvarado (n.d.), A. Preparation, Recruitment, and Retention of Teachers. Retrieved February 25, 2015 from <http://www.unesco.org/iiep/PDF/Edpol5.pdf>
- [6] Cortez, B. (2014). EDITORIAL: Brigada Eskwela. Retrieved October 19, 2014, from <https://northwatch.wordpress.com/2014/05/26/editorial-brigada-eskwela/>
- [7] Department of Education Brigada Eskwela National Schools Maintenance Program Manual for School Heads, p. 2-4
- [8] DepEd Order No. 100, s. 2009 - Launching Brigada Eskwela Plus and Directing Selected Public Schools to Volunteer in this Community Involvement in Education Initiative
- [9] DepEd Regional Memorandum No. 105 s. 2014. Regional Implementation of 2014 Innovative Brigada Eskwela.
- [10] Doblón, A. (2011). Brigada Eskwela: A Powerhouse for Unity, Cleanliness, and School Development. *The Modern Teacher*. Volume 60, p.11-12
- [11] Emeagwali, S. (2009). Fostering Parent-Teacher Collaboration in the Classroom Techniques (Association for Career and Technical Education). *Techniques: Connecting Education & Careers*; Vol. 84 Issue 5, p8.
- [12] Epstein, J., Sanders, M., Sheldon, S., Simon B., Salinas, K., Jansorn, N., et al. (2009). *School, Family, and Community Partnerships: Your Handbook for Action*. Thousand Oaks, CA:Corwin.
- [13] Espidido, Narmela P. (2010). Parental Involvement and Participation on the Academic Practices in Schools Encouraged. *The Modern Teacher*. Volume 59, p. 7-9.
- [14] Family-School Partnerships Framework. A guide for schools and families. Retrieved November 4, 2014 from http://www.partners4learning.edu.au/_uploads/_ckpg/files/FamilySchoolPartnershipsFrameworkFINAL-1.pdf
- [15] Fraenkel, J., & Wallen, N. (2009). *How to Design and Evaluate Research in Education*. 7th Edition:McGraw-Hill.
- [16] Gordon, M., & Louis, K.S. (2009). Linking Parent and Community Involvement with Student Achievement: Comparing Principal and Teacher Perceptions of Stakeholder Influence. *American Journal of Education*, Vol. 116. Retrieved October 6, 2014, from <http://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ858941>.

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and LearningVol. 10, Issue 3, pp: (43-62), Month: May - June 2023, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

- [17] Henderson, A. (2011). Family-School-Community Partnerships 2.0 Collaborative Strategies to Advance Student Learning. National Education Association.
- [18] Herrell, P. (2011). Parental Involvement: Parent Perceptions and Teacher Perceptions. Department of Educational Leadership and Policy Analysis East Tennessee State University.
- [19] Kilgore, E. (2014). Teacher Home Visits: The Importance of Sharing a Meal. Retrieved March 13, 2015 from <http://www.edweek.org/tm/articles/2014/03/10/kp-kilgore.html>
- [20] Koch, C. (2014). Home-School-Community Partnerships. Illinois State Board of Education. Retrieved January 17, 2015, from <http://www.isbe.net/learningsupports/html/partnerships.htm>
- [21] Leithwood, K. et.al. (n.d.) Seven Strong Claims About Successful School Leadership. National College for School Leadership. Retrieved February 20, 2015 from <http://dera.ioe.ac.uk/6967/1/download%3Fid%3D17387%26filename%3Dseven-claims-about-successful-school-leadership.pdf> and http://illinoisschoolleader.org/research_compodium/documents/successful_school_leadership.pdf
- [22] Liguton, J. (2009). Governance in the Education Sector. Philippine Institute for Development Studies. Volume 27, p. 2.
- [23] Little, P. (2011). School-Community Learning Partnerships: Essential to Expanded Learning Success. Retrieved January 16, 2015, from <http://expandinglearning.org/expandingminds/article/school-community-learning-partnerships-essential-expanded-learning-success> London, England:Routledge
- [24] Mendoza, M. (2013). Parents' Attitude on PTA Activities, Their Children's Classroom Participation and Academic Success.
- [25] Midtimbang, A. (2012). Teachers' Perception Towards Participation in Community Activities and Its Relationship to Their Community Involvement.
- [26] National Competency-Based Teacher Standards: Experiential Learning Courses Handbook a Project of Teacher Education Council (TEC), Department of Education (DepED), and Commission On Education (CHED)
- [27] Obrien, A. (2014). When Teachers and Administrators Collaborate. Retrieved March 15, 2015 from <http://www.edutopia.org/blog/when-teachers-and-administrators-collaborate-anne-obrien>
- [28] Olsen, G. & Fuller, M. L. (2010). The Benefits of Parent Involvement: What Research Has to Say. January 22, 2015 from <http://www.education.com/reference/article/benefits-parent-involvement-research/>
- [29] Peter, U. (2012). Importance of School Plant to the Teaching-Learning Process. Namse's Blog. Retrieved March 17, 2015 from <https://namse.wordpress.com/2012/08/01/importance-of-school-plant-to-the-teaching-learning-process/>
- [30] Republic Act 8525. An Act Establishing An "Adopt-a-School Program," Providing Incentives Therefor, And For Other Purposes
- [31] Salinas, K., Epstein, J., Sanders, M., Davis, D., Douglas, I. (2009). Measure of School,
- [32] Family, and Community Partnerships. Northwest Regional Educational Laboratory and National Network of Partnership Schools. International Education Studies; Vol. 6, No. 1: Canadian Center of Science and Education
- [33] Sibayan, T. (2012). BRIGADA ESKWELA 2012: Making the School a Home for Learning. Retrieved October 16, 2014, from <https://dampeelementaryschool.wordpress.com/2012/10/16/brigada-eskwela/>.
- [34] Soterno, G. (2009). Perceived Roles of Parents and Level of Participation in School Activities: A Basis for an Enhanced Home-School Link Program.
- [35] Wherry, J. (2009). Shattering Barriers to Parent Involvement. University of Alberta.

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